

Some New Coumarins: Condensation of Malon-*p*-phenetidic Acid with Salicylaldehyde and Substituted Salicylaldehydes

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Malon-*p*-phenetidic acid has been condensed with salicylaldehyde, 5-chloro-, 3,5-dichloro-, 5-bromo-, 3,5-dibromo-, 3,5-di-iodo-, 5-nitro-, 3,5-dinitro- and 5-chloro-3-nitro-salicylaldehydes, using different condensing agents. The corresponding coumarins and Schiff's bases have been prepared and identified. A trace of pyridine has been found to act as the best catalyst.

In an earlier communication¹, the preparation of malon-*p*-phenetidic acid and of some of its derivatives have been described. The present communication deals with the preparation of some substituted coumarins (I) by condensing the above acid with salicylaldehyde and some substituted salicylaldehydes. All these aldehydes were prepared by well-known methods. The condensations were carried out either alone or in presence of a trace of pyridine, piperidine, or polyphosphoric acid. Pyridine in traces was found to be the best catalyst.

The general method of condensation involves heating an equimolecular mixture of the acid and the aldehyde in an oil bath at 100-105° for 4 hr. The mass first melted to a clear liquid and this in course of time set to a solid. In experiments where the condensing agent was used, a drop of the agent was added to the above mixture. The product was found to be invariably a mixture of (I) and (II) and in no case product (III) was obtained.

The formation of Schiff's bases (II) seems to be a peculiar feature of the *o*-hydroxy-aldehyde condensation alone. This observation was made in this laboratory by Bhukta and Ittyerah² also. A part of malon-*p*-phenetidic acid is hydrolysed during the reaction and the amine thus released condenses with the aldehyde. The identity of this product

1. Singhal *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1965, 42, 479.

2. *Ibid.*, 1955, 42, 455.

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has been established both by analysis and by mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen prepared by condensation of *p*-phenetidine with the respective aldehyde.

The coumarins obtained are yellow to orange in colour and their yields range from 4-48%. Schiff's bases are orange to scarlet-red with 2-24% yield. The coumarin was separated from Schiff's base by fractional crystallisation from ethanol in which the former was very sparingly soluble. In all cases the coumarins were recrystallised from glacial acetic acid and Schiff's bases, from ethanol.

EXPERIMENTAL

Condensation of Malon-p-phenetidic Acid with Salicylaldehyde.—Malon *p*-phenetidic acid (1.1g.), salicylaldehyde (0.56 g.) and a drop of pyridine were heated in an oil bath at 100-105° for 10 hr. The yellow solid mass was then digested with a saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate (10 ml). The alkali extract was decanted and the residue washed well with water. The alkali extract on acidification with HCl (conc.) did not form any precipitate. The residue was boiled with ethanol (15 ml) and filtered. The ethanolic extract on concentration and cooling provided a very small amount (2%) of 2-hydroxybenzylidene-*p* phenetidine, m.p. 95°. (Found: N, 5.62. C₁₅H₁₅ON requires N, 5.80%). The identity of this was further confirmed by synthesising an authentic specimen from *p*-phenetidine and salicylaldehyde.

The residue left after boiling with ethanol was recrystallised from glacial acetic acid as yellow crystals of coumarin-3-carboxy-*p*-phenetidide; yield 48%, m.p. 210-11°. (Found: N, 4.71. C₁₈H₁₅O₄N, requires N, 4.53%).

The other aldehydes were condensed with malon-*p*-phenetidic acid in the same manner and the products extracted as described above. The effect of different condensing agents was also studied. The coumarins and Schiff's bases obtained along with their analytical results, m.p. etc. are recorded in Tables I and II.

TABLE I
Coumarins.

No.	Name.	Formula.	M.P.	% Nitrogen	
				Found.	Reqd.
1	*R	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₄ N	210-11°	4.71	4.53
2	6-Chloro-R	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₄ NCl	218°	4.00	4.07
3	6,8-Dichloro-R	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₄ NCl ₂	235°	3.64	3.70
4	6-Bromo-R	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₄ NBr	210°	3.54	3.60
5	6,8-Dibromo-R	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₄ NBr ₂	214°	3.05	2.99
6	6,8-Di-iodo-R	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₄ NI ₂	251°	2.30	2.49
7	6-Nitro-R	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₆ N ₂	243°	7.78	7.90
8	6,8-Dinitro-R	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₈ N ₃	> 300°	10.38	10.52
9	6-Chloro-8-nitro-R	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₆ N ₂ Cl	273°	7.30	7.20

*R stands for coumarin-3-carboxy-*p*-phenetidide.

TABLE II
Schiff's bases.

No.	Name.	Formula.	M.P.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
1	*R	$C_{15}H_{15}O_2N$	95-96°	5.62	5.80
2	2-Hydroxy-5-chloro-R	$C_{15}H_{14}O_2NCl$	144°	4.99	5.08
3	2-Hydroxy-3,5-dichloro-R	$C_{15}H_{13}O_2NCl_2$	132°	4.78	4.50
4	2-Hydroxy-5-bromo-R	$C_{15}H_{14}O_2NBr$	150°	4.30	4.37
5	2-Hydroxy-3,5-dibromo-R	$C_{15}H_{13}O_2NBr_2$	152°	3.20	3.50
6	2-Hydroxy-3,5-di-iodo-R	$C_{15}H_{13}O_2NI_2$	138°	2.65	2.83
7	2-Hydroxy-5-nitro-R	$C_{15}H_{14}O_4N_2$	173°	9.83	9.79
8	2-Hydroxy-3,5-dinitro-R	$C_{15}H_{13}O_6N_3$	242°	12.10	12.64
9	2-Hydroxy-5-chloro-3-nitro-R	$C_{15}H_{13}O_4N_2Cl$	153°	8.78	8.70

*R stands for benzylidene-*p*-phenetidine.

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